

EDITORIAL

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In the spring of 2016, Dr. Steven R. Harmon, Visiting Associate Professor of Historical Theology, Gardner-Webb University School of Divinity, released the latest installment in his ecumenical pilgrimage, *Baptist Identity and the Ecumenical Future: Story, Tradition, and the Recovery of Community* (Baylor University Press). Author of numerous scholarly articles and books such as *Ecumenism Means You, Too* (2010) and *Towards Baptist Catholicity: Essays on Tradition and the Baptist Vision* (2006), Professor Harmon has invested a substantial portion of his career and life's energy on the ecumenical question and the relationship of Baptists to the broader Christian tradition. I have known Steve personally for many years now, and one thing I have come to respect and admire about him is his careful, conscientious, even meticulous attention to detail—and this book is no exception. It is a true labour of love.

Because Harmon's new book spans the interests of the National Association of Baptist Professors of Religion and the Baptist History & Heritage Society, and because the two groups convened simultaneously on the campus of Baylor University's Truett Theological Seminary in May of 2016, the conference organisers were presented with a timely opportunity to hold a joint panel discussion on the topic of *Baptist Identity and the Ecumenical Future*. Courtney Pace, Assistant Professor of Church History, Memphis Theological Seminary, represented the Baptist History & Heritage Society alongside Andrew Smith, Assistant Professor of Religion, Carson-Newman University. Amy L. Chilton Thompson, Adjunct Professor, Fuller Theological Seminary and Azusa Pacific University, and David Wilhite, Associate Professor of Christian Theology, George W. Truett Theological Seminary, represented the National Association of Baptist Professors of Religion. Each panelist was allotted twelve minutes to offer comments, after which time Steve Harmon had a chance to respond. The review essays included in this volume have retained the spoken, live-event character of the panel discussion in the hopes that the reader will catch the sounds and cadences of the lively conversation that took place.

The National Association of Baptist Professors of Religion and the Baptist History & Heritage Society extend their gratitude to the *Pacific Journal of Baptist Research* for the opportunity to showcase the scholarly work of their respective members and extend the conversation.